

Currents of Control:

Ownership evolutions in the submarine data cable industry

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Abstract

The article examines global submarine data cable projects from 1989 to 2028 to explore the evolving political economy of digital media and communication infrastructures. Focusing on the growing number of new cable projects and their ownership, we identify several phases of network expansion, which correspond with different types of market dominance and ownership constellations. That is, in the early phases of submarine cable buildout, the main market actors were national and regional telecommunications corporations, often collaborating in large consortia, whereas the later phases see a growing concentration of ownership around a set of global market actors, often establishing their own networks to support their extensive platform and data businesses. In interpreting this development, we seek inspiration from previous historical analyses of large-scale technological systems and argue that the internet has reached a momentum where its built-in affordances lead to a fundamental shift in institutional power. We end by discussing the implications of this historical transformation, emphasizing that the new generations of cable systems amplify an already walled-off ecosystem, where access to the superior infrastructure is conditioned by the usage of proprietary services, leading to a reintegration of the network and service layer that the internet originally separated.

Keywords

Submarine data cables; internet infrastructure; technological momentum; political economy; media history.

Introduction

Global technology corporations like Google, Meta, and Amazon, whose businesses grew out of supplying vital software and platforms for communication, search, social media, retailing and more, increasingly expand their assets to also include hardware and network components – from server stacks nested side by side in monumental data centers to mobile towers scattered across remote planes. (Plantin and Punathambekar, 2019). Moving beyond their original domains and harnessing the technical and financial resources raised as part of their lucrative platform businesses, these corporations position themselves as key infrastructure suppliers across the digital value chain. As yet another frontier for tech expansionism, attention has recently turned to the global submarine data cable market with news coverage and industry hype suggesting that US-based hyperscalers are “colonizing the seabed” (Pinaud, 2023) and “reshaping the submarine cable industry” (Kang and Jacob, 2024).

With up to 99% of all intercontinental data traffic travelling through submarine cables (Mauldin, 2023), this part of the internet infrastructure creates significant dependencies and bottlenecks, placing its owners and suppliers at key positions in the digital market and society at large. Submarine data cables, in other words, constitute a central empirical entry point for studying contemporary formations of power as they are quite literally built into the physical environment that digital societies rest upon. As we argue in this paper, the ongoing expansion of platform corporations into the internet backbone amplifies an already walled-off ecosystem, where access to the superior infrastructure is conditioned by the usage of proprietary services, leading to a reintegration of the network and service layer that the internet originally separated.

Despite growing concerns about the market power of platform corporations and the critical nature of submarine data infrastructures for global connectivity and communication capacities, scholarly research on the topic is scarce, with no up-to-date empirical analyses tracing the shifting ownership constellations in the industry as a whole and over time. While submarine cables are an evident object of analysis for the growing number of internet infrastructure studies (Musiani et al., 2016; Plantin et al., 2018; Plantin and Punathambekar, 2019; Sandvig, 2013), few explicitly engage with the changing ownership and underlying business models of these networks (Munn, 2020).

Contributing to an emergent political economist turn in internet infrastructure studies (Hesmondhalgh, 2021), this article sets out to identify and discuss key developments in the submarine data cable industry from the late 1980s to the present day. In light of the recent rise in new and extensive cable connections, we pay particular attention to the increasing

concentration of power around single global corporations replacing former multi-stakeholder consortia models (Lehdonvirta and Mikelsaar, 2025) and investigate the underlying business models and market conditions that have led to this historical shift. In doing so, we critically discuss how the shifting ownership arrangements in the submarine industry reflect and amplify broader power asymmetries in the digital market and the implications thereof.

State of the art

Illustrating the multidimensional and complex questions invoked by submarine data networks, existing research on this topic is scattered across a range of disciplines including Media Studies (Bojczuk et al., 2024; Starosielski, 2015), Geography (Malecki and Wei, 2009; Xie and Wang, 2023), Law (Beckman, 2010; Raha and Raju, 2021), and Cyber Security (Bueger and Liebetrau, 2021; Gjesvik, 2022). While enquiries into network control, state sovereignty, and commercial interests are recurrent across these studies, few explicitly engage with questions of ownership and historical reconfigurations of the submarine data cable industry.

Nicole Starosielski's *The Undersea Network* (2015) traces the historical, political, and geographic features of submarine data cables, placing important emphasis on how colonial and postcolonial powers continue to influence the evolution of these networks. Dan Schiller's (2023) comprehensive account of the "history of US telecommunications, from the post office to the Internet" also points to submarine cables as a long-standing arena for regional and global geopolitics. Yet, written before the recent boom in cable investments, neither explicitly touches upon the role of platform corporations nor empirically analyzes the shifting ownership structures around this critical communication resource.

As an empirical backdrop for our study, Dwayne Winseck's (2017, 2019) work on "the geopolitical economy of the global internet infrastructure" places submarine data cables as a central indicator for testing "the persistent myth of US hegemony". Based on a mapping of the ownership of submarine data cables, he concludes that US-based (platform) companies did not (at the time of writing) "rule the 'guts and the gears' — the hardware, the material infrastructure — of the internet" (115). Instead, he shows how public and private companies from, for instance, China and India, have become important players in the submarine cable industry and beyond. There is, however, little empirical evidence of how the global control over submarine cables has evolved since these studies – a period characterized by a wealth

of cables retiring and new high-capacity networks emerging as results of innovations in AI and cloud computing.

As a rare example of a study that addresses the more recent developments in the submarine data cable industry (see also Thorat, 2020), Esther Mwema and Abeba Birhane (2024) trace the establishment of new, major networks in the oceans surrounding the African continent, focusing on two new cable projects: Meta's 45,000 kilometers 2Africa cable connecting Africa, Europe and Asia through 33 countries, and Google's Equiano cable linking Africa to Europe via Portugal. Examining how these connections follow historical trade routes, they argue that these cable networks replicate colonial logics of extractivism and exploitation. While case studies such as this sensitize us to ongoing infrastructure developments and the implications thereof, they also call for analyses approaching the more general trajectories of the industry and the position and strategies of the new market entrants.

Beyond academic publications, a wealth of knowledge can be found in industry reports from telecommunications corporations and the respective industry media. *Telegeography*, for instance, presents extensive analyses of developments in the submarine industry, including the transition of "contents providers" such as Google, Meta, Microsoft and Amazon "from just being customers of wholesale capacity to owning transport network infrastructure" (Mauldin, 2024). As another example, *Submarine Telecom's* newest industry report offers "detailed system maps, market share breakdowns, and company profiles that reflect the evolving balance between private investment and consortium-led infrastructure" (Clark, 2025). While these outlets constitute essential sources of information and inspiration for our study, they were not developed for academic studies and, as such, require critical scrutiny. Scholarly enquiries are, in other words, essential to substantiate, qualify, and contextualise public discussions and industry intel.

Theoretical framework

Approaching the evolution in submarine data cables from a political economist perspective, our study follows the trajectory of a long-standing tradition for critical research into the infrastructural foundations of media and communication empires (Hardy, 2014; Mansell, 1993; Wasko, 2004). At the heart of these studies is an understanding of ownership of network infrastructures as essential for understanding how dominant market actors come to enable and constrain, guide and steer, undergird and profit from people's everyday communication. In this sense, the power of media institutions goes beyond their symbolic

positions as content providers to also include a more fundamental influence on how communication environments are organised and controlled (Innis, 2007).

In digital societies, this form of infrastructural power (Munn, 2020) is intrinsically tied to so-called Big Tech actors or hyperscalers that control key technologies across the different layers of the internet stack (Cohen, 2024). Designing and supplying underlying software systems such as app stores, operating systems, and third-party integrations (Binns et al., 2018; Dieter et al., 2019; Helmond, 2015), companies like Google, Meta, Amazon, and Microsoft create dependencies that perpetually confirm and reinforce their dominance in the digital ecosystem (Srnicsek, 2024; van Dijck et al., 2019). Yet, recent investments into submarine systems constitute a crucial, though understudied, extension of platform power into network infrastructure (Nieborg and Poell, 2025; Plantin et al., 2018).

The recent surge in submarine data cable buildout is, in other words, part of a larger societal restructuring where the internet has evolved from a supplementary communication tool to a general-purpose technology (Naughton, 2016). To gauge this historical development, we draw on Thomas P. Hughes' momentum theory (1983, 1987) as a middle-ground approach to engage with both the institutional continuity and the transformative potentials of new technologies (Jensen, 2013).

Following the momentum theory, young technological systems take shape from the institutional and cultural contexts in which they emerge, while more mature systems have the potential to alter the societies that come to rely upon them. That is, the first phases of a technology's lifespan, it is developed in a certain institutional context, reflecting existing political and economic power structures that are then transferred beyond the original domain. A successful "transfer" results in a technological as well as commercial acceleration, moving the system into a phase of "growth", where it supports a broad range of activities, creates economic surplus, and often leads to increasing competition (Hughes, 1987: 29). "Technological momentum" occurs when the material features of the (new) system has become an integral part of society's infrastructure. In this phase, the technology will reconfigure the physical foundation upon which established institutional arrangements are built and alter basic societal modes of control (Beniger, 1986), thereby displaying what Hughes refers to as "soft determinism" (1987: 6).

Originally developed for socio-technical analyses of electrification, Hughes emphasizes historical events such as particular technological breakthroughs, political decisions, or industry strategies as empirical entry points for studying system development. In our adaptation of the momentum theory for the study of the political economy of submarine

data cables, we instead shift the focus towards broader structural and macroscopic changes. Rather than detailing the technological development of fiber optic technologies or unpacking how individual cables are governed, we scrutinize the overarching dynamics, specifically, how control over access to and use of critical infrastructural resources shifts over time. This also entails de-emphasizing the highly contextual and situational factors that surely influence the development of submarine data cables in favor of providing a broader empirical assessment of the fundamental restructuring of power at the backbone of the digital societies.

Research design & methods

In assessing the evolution of submarine data cable systems, we focus on three analytical dimensions: 1) the gradual *buildout* of new submarine data cables, 2) the shifting *sectoral* arrangements, and 3) the degrees of *ownership* concentration. We approach the dimension of buildout by looking at the fluctuations of investments in the industry over time; assess the sectoral organization by gauging the positions of, respectively, legacy telecommunication companies, new market entrants coming from a variety of other sectors, and platform corporations; and investigate the consolidation of ownership by studying the relative distribution of single- or few-owner constellations and large consortia models over the period. This way, we trace how the global submarine data cable industry has evolved alongside the gradual increase in global connectivity, the spread of high-capacity innovations, and the historical reconfigurations of the digital economy.

The analysis builds on a relational database containing information on cables in operation as of January 2025, planned cables with an RFS date up until 2028, and historical cable projects from 1989 onwards. Importantly, many of the older cables remain on the ocean floor with little to no data traffic due to outdated technology and poor capacity, by now simply acting as backups. Other, newer cables sit there as ‘dark fiber’ waiting to be lit up by expected increases in demand for capacity. Moreover, some cable projects are in planning for years but end up never being realized due to, for instance, lack of funding or geopolitical constraints, while finally, a bulk of projects are projected for the years 2026 to 2028 and not yet operational. As such, the analysis focuses on cable *projects* as the units of analysis, emphasizing the commercial interests in investing and controlling this infrastructural resource, rather than on the actual existence of the cables.

Data collection

All data stems from publicly available data sources, predominantly the telecom intelligence company TeleGeography (n.d.) – parts of it were obtained through its GitHub before this

closed in 2021. The remaining years were scraped from the visual interface of their Submarine Cable Map. Providing market intelligence, TeleGeography collects data directly from industry partners, including cable owners and carriers and augments this with publicly available information (e.g., cable landing licenses from national regulatory authorities). While TeleGeography constitutes a well-recognized and highly cited data source, the Submarine Cable Map also poses methodological challenges to historical analyses: Once cables are taken out of operation or replaced, they disappear from the map, meaning that the current database does not convey information on cables that once were. As cables usually have a lifespan of 20 to 25 years, and our analysis stretches from 1989, many cables no longer appear on the map. We therefore employed a suite of methods to reconstruct the missing data on historical cable projects and contemporary buildouts, including the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine (n.d.) to access archived versions of the Submarine Cable Map and traversing historical datasets from industry partners and other sources including news media, market reports, and corporate press releases (Mahlknecht, n.d.; Submarine Networks, n.d.; SubTel Forum, n.d.).

As with many other commercially run data services, TeleGeography is a business-to-business (B2B) service catering to a large and growing industry seeking intel for qualifying “cable investments, designing cloud-based networks, researching international markets, and benchmarking their services against competitors” (TeleGeography, n.d.). As such, like other commercial data repositories and portals, using them for academic purposes comes with a suite of constraints and conflicts resulting from the volatility of the methods.

As opposed to primary data collection, the use of secondary (like the datasets in the GitHub) or even tertiary data sources (like the map) leaves little room for deciding over measures, variables, and samples, and even less for questioning the data beyond what is published. Like social media APIs or web measurements (Venturini and Rogers, 2019), these data are often used to inquire into some of the same industry actors that depart the data in the first place. In this case, the Submarine Cable Map is funded by AquaComms, and before them, by Huawei and Equinix – all established actors in the industry and therefore concurrently data funders and objects of analysis. With these services opening and closing on a regular basis, the researcher is inherently at the mercy of (some of) the very same actors that she aims to study (Flensburg et al., 2025).

Data processing

Our dataset comprises all information available through the submarine cable map, including cable names, IDs, lengths, landing stations, countries connected, owners, and suppliers. For

the historical cables, we have collected information from press releases, archived websites, and industry reports to mirror TeleGeography's data structure. Upon collection, we have recoded the data in accordance with our research questions and developed measures enabling us to make calculations across the three dimensions outlined above:

First, the dataset contains information on the number of cable projects per year and the length of each cable, enabling us to assess the growth in cable connections. To be able to calculate potential sectoral changes over time, we have recoded the individual owners of each cable for sectoral affiliation, distinguishing between 'telcos', 'platforms', 'states', and 'others'. The 'telco' category includes legacy telecommunication operators, for fixed as well as mobile, but excludes newer internet service providers (e.g., ISPs supplying connections based on fiber, etc.). The 'platform' category comprises leading software and data corporations, often originating in Silicon Valley, including Google, Amazon, Microsoft, and Meta. It in principle includes the Chinese platform competitors – Baidu, Alibaba, Tencent, and Xiaomi – but these do not figure in the data. The 'state' category comprises projects where a nation state appears as the owning entity. Finally, the 'other' category comprises smaller IT companies, media and broadcast corporations, energy and utility companies, fiber companies, investment companies, joint ventures, and so forth.

Especially for the older cables, many are owned by large consortia (often national telcos collaborating on longer, cross-country or -continent cables), meaning that the position of some corporations and sectors can come out artificially enlarged (e.g., the French telco, Orange, is involved in numerous cables, but with a wealth of other actors acting as co-owners). Since there is no publicly available and authoritative information on the ownership *shares* of individual companies in all cable consortia, we assess the ownership position of each company – and thereby the sector to which they belong – according to the size of the consortia. That is, if a cable is owned by 10 different companies, each of these will be assigned a weight of 0,1, when calculating their position in the submarine cable market. This allows us to also calculate their position according to the length of the cable projects, meaning that companies and sectors that hold sole ownership of (longer) cables will figure more prominently in our dataset than companies and sectors that share ownership of (shorter) cable routes.

Analysis

Approaching the history of the submarine data cable industry, we first analyze the full period from 1989 to 2028 diachronically to identify key tendencies and turning points. We then identify three overarching stages in this evolution, each characterized by distinct

technological and political-economic conditions. That is, we approach the overarching patterns and changes synchronically by linking the characteristics of each phase to the three analytical dimensions outlined above.

Submarine data cable evolutions

Focusing on the *buildout* dimension, we find an overall growth in both the number and length of cable projects across the period from 1989 to 2028, with more cable systems operating in 2025 than in any other year (Burdette, 2025). Figure 1 illustrates the yearly distribution of the 804 projects according to their RFS year. In contrast, Figure 2 displays the length of cable projects for each year, with a total length of 2.443.827 kilometers of cable appearing in our dataset.

[Figure 1 here]

[Figure 2 here]

The gradual buildout fluctuates significantly across the graphs' 40-year span, reflecting several peaks as well drops in cable projects: From 1989 to the early 2000s, we see an overall increase in both the number and length of new cable projects, peaking with a total of 35 cables in 1999 and 209.195 kilometers of cable being laid across 26 cables in 2001. Several of these ventures cross the Atlantic and Pacific oceans, connecting US to Europe, Asia, and South America. The 2000s, in turn, represent a period of relative decline in cable laying, with a low point of 9 cable projects in 2003, and the average length of new cables dropping to 8.214 km in 2007. By 2019, the number of new cable projects soars again to 39, where several new projects are projected to raise the bar for global submarine cable networks.

Turning to the *sector* dimension, Figure 3 illustrates the positions of 'telcos', 'platforms', 'states', and 'others' appearing as owners of different cable projects across the 40-year period, whereas Figure 4 illustrates the total length of those cable projects. The visualizations broadly show that the submarine data cable industry of the early 1990s was heavily dominated by legacy telecommunications operators such as Orange, British Telecom (BT), and AT&T, often organized in large consortia representing the countries in which the cables would land. The spike in new cable projects around the turn of the century introduced a new and diverse set of actors, including newly established, independent internet service providers (ISPs), energy companies, and media corporations. We also find several standalone companies established with the sole purpose of obtaining funding for building and operating specific cable connections and actors dedicated specifically to the submarine cable business.

[Figure 3 here]

[Figure 4 here]

The emergence and steady increase of platform corporations from 2010 does not appear disruptive when looking solely at the number of cable projects they are involved in. Yet, when accounting for the length of these projects, it becomes apparent that the networks funded by platform corporations are more extensive than those of the telcos and companies in the ‘other’ category. The telco-led projects, in contrast, tend to get shorter throughout the period from 1989 to 2028.

Finally, Figure 5 visualizes the *ownership* dimension, measured on the average number of owners per cable project. It shows a gradual increase in the number of actors collaborating on cable projects throughout the 1990s, reflecting the growing size, complexity, and global reach of the cable networks. While the early 1990s were characterized by predominantly national and regional projects, owned by one or a few actors, the spike in cable projects around the year 2000 was accompanied by an equivalent spike in the number of owners per cable: from an average of 1,8 owners per cable in 1992 to 5,6 in 2002. Figure 6 shows the distribution of cable projects owned by, respectively, single companies, small consortia (2-4 companies), and large consortia (5+ companies). In the 1990s, these consortia largely consisted of national telecommunications companies collaborating on connecting their home markets, often across the world oceans (e.g., the cross-Atlantic TAT-14 and APCN2 cables, crossing the Chinese Seas, both of which involve more than 20 companies).

[Figure 5 here]

[Figure 6 here]

In the period after the drop in buildouts in the early 2000s, the average number of cable owners declined again, reflecting the shorter routes and less complex projects being established in this period. While 2004 marks an absolute low point in co-ownership (an average of 1,1 owners per cable), we see a gradual increase up until 2012, where each cable on average has 3,0 owners. After 2012, the average number of owners of a cable declines rapidly, with more than half (22 cables) of all the cables becoming ready for service in 2025 (40 cables) being owned by single corporations (e.g., Google’s Firmina and TPU cables, and Meta’s Anjana cable). The projections for 2026, 2027, and 2028 follow this trajectory, with 22 of 33 planned projects in 2026 being single-owned cable systems. Seven of these are owned by Google alone, including the two extensive Pacific cables, Bulikula and

Honomoana. In 2027 nine out of 14 cables are single owned, and for 2028 this is five of six cables in total.

Based on the developments outlined above, we distinguish between three overall periods in the history of the submarine data cable industry: an early phase of *transfer*, spanning from 1989 to approximately 2002, where a wide range of new connections were established and legacy telcos positioned themselves as key gatekeepers of the increasingly global internet; a middle phase of technological *growth* from around 2003 to 2018 where the number of cable projects is staggering but a new set of actors entered the market alongside the rise of a wide range of new technologies at other layers of the internet's infrastructure and a general rise in connectivity; and a final and ongoing *momentum* phase from 2019 where old cables are being retired and gradually replaced by new, high-capacity systems, increasingly financed and owned by platform corporations operating in smaller consortia or alone.

Transfer – the legacy club

The early submarine data cable evolution was characterized by a gradual expansion in the geographic scope of the systems – from cable projects connecting mainly European and North American contexts in the early 1990s to a more diverse set of landing points towards the early 2000s. While the first projects were quite humble in size, several cables spanning world oceans and connecting North and South America as well as Europe, Asia, and to some extent Africa were reported ready for service in the period up to 2002. That is, although the number of cables increases over the years until 2028, the average length of cable projects in the transfer phase (3,152,4 km) remains higher than in the subsequent growth phase, when much of the global wiring of the oceans had already been completed.

The significant buildout of the transfer phase corresponds with the public breakthrough of the internet, the gradual influx of new applications extending its use (World Wide Web, chat forums, gaming, etc.), a rapid growth user numbers around the turn of the century, and the derived need to transfer increasing flows of digital data. It is also related to the broader privatization of the internet's backbone and gradual commercial re-organization of the early internet (Naughton, 2016).

In this period, legacy telcos and incumbents transfer existing networks for telephony, invest their economic surplus, and deploy their technological expertise to position themselves as market leaders of early submarine internet connectivity. That is, accounting for 62% of all cable lengths in the transfer period, the central position of the 'telco' category can be viewed

as a direct consequence of their existing infrastructural assets, investment power, and personnel. With landline (and increasingly mobile) telephony still being a strong source of income, internet provision constituted an attractive add-on to an already successful business model at the time.

Being costly business ventures, submarine connections between different national contexts were often accomplished through consortia collaboration between telcos. As such, while 27,8% of cables in the transfer phase are smaller single owned cables, the remaining rely on consortia as big as 33 different companies establishing lengthy routes between continents. In the 1990s and towards the turn of the millennium, investments in internet businesses are booming and telecommunications companies are reaping the benefits of this to increase capacities and speeds in the networks. After the dot-com bubble burst around the year 2000, however, investment slowed down rapidly, and the buildout of the submarine cable infrastructure followed its trajectory. This signals the onset of the next phase of exponential growth in global internet traffic and a beginning reconfiguration of the sectoral arrangements and business models shaping the submarine data cable industry.

Growth – a digital goldrush

Marking the end of the transfer phase, the period starting around 2003 is characterized by technological and commercial acceleration with a wealth of new digital services emerging including voice (and video) over IP (Skype launches in 2003), social media sites (e.g., (the) Facebook in 2005)), and video streaming (from YouTube in 2005 to Netflix in 2007). In accordance with Hughes' (1983) notion of system *growth* (64), the internet comes to undergird a broad range of activities, accompanied by enhanced competition across the digital industries, including that of submarine data cables. The proliferation of high-capacity innovations and rapid increase in internet users put pressure on the existing network infrastructure, resulting in an increase in cable buildout over the period, from a yearly average of 16,2 cable projects from 1989 to 2002 to 19,3 in the period from 2003 to 2018. The size of the cables, however, decrease (to 2.741 km on average) compared to those of the previous phase.

While submarine data cables are crucial to the comprehensive digitalization in the growth phase, cable *laying* becomes increasingly complex with a multitude of different market actors rushing to invest in an infrastructure that is seen as essential for a range of anticipated innovations. Relatedly, the growth phase also encompasses several cable projects that were never realized due to funding deficits, increased competition, and budding geopolitical instabilities (Flensburg and Lai, 2025). In most cases, the companies behind these projects

belong to the ‘other’ category, meaning that the share of these actors might be less significant if we had looked only at *established* cable networks rather than also cable projects in the making.

While the submarine cable market expands (from a total of 187 unique market actors in the transfer phase to 302 in the growth phase), the ownership shares of the ‘telco’ and ‘other’ categories remain largely the same. Despite the diversity in market actors, we see a burgeoning decline in big consortia cables, expressed in the average number of owners decreasing from 2.4 in the first phase to 2.0 in the latter and the share of single-owned cable projects going in the opposite direction, from 28% to 38% of all cables. That is, more cables are established by only one or a few companies, suggesting that the economic divide between smaller and more regional actors on the one hand, and large global corporations on the other, is widening.

In this phase, we also find a small group of new entrants from the platform business, including Meta, Google, Microsoft, and Amazon. To begin with, these corporation engage in consortia with other established actors: Google and several telcos build the Unity cable in 2010; Meta joins the three big Chinese telcos in a consortium to build the Asia Pacific Gateway in 2016; and Meta and Microsoft join forces with Telxius on the MAREA project in 2018. As such, the first examples of platform-financed buildout follow patterns of institutional continuity, in the sense that these actors enter the market on the established terms for cable laying, only to eventually alter the rules of the game from within as we see in the subsequent momentum phase.

Momentum – new incumbents?

With submarine data cables supporting a wealth of societal functions and everyday life activities, this part of the internet infrastructure undeniably constitutes what Hughes (1983) terms a “high-momentum system” (41). While the early phase of submarine data cable buildout enabled the emergence and rollout of a new communication technology that piggy-backed on existing infrastructures, technological expertise, and economic resources in the telecommunications sector, the internet has now proven to be the superior system, pushing its predecessors to the periphery and paving the way for new business models and market actors.

Many of the cable systems that were built in the booming years around the turn of the millennium have reached their lifespan and are now being retired, while high-capacity innovations in, for instance, AI and cloud computing are pushing demands upwards for both

new and more powerful cable systems. Compared to the leap in the average number of cable projects per year from 16.2 in the first period to 19.3 in the second, we now see a substantial increase with 26.7 cable projects per year and an average length of 3.288,5 kilometers per cable, thereby surpassing both previous periods. While projections for 2027 and 2028 do not disclose a high number of cables, the ones in planning are, by all comparisons, excessively large-scale projects like Meta's Waterworth cable system, set to span five continents and over 50,000 kilometers (Nagarajan and Aimé, 2025).

Although the 'telco' category still comes out as the largest when looking at the ownership of the total number of cables in the period (46%), it is surpassed by the 'other' category when calculating its share based on length (39% for 'other' and 34% for 'telcos'). The 'other' category, as mentioned, comprises a wide range of different actors, amongst which the ones involved in most cable projects are the dedicated infrastructure companies AquaComms and Bulk (both of which collaborate with platform corporations on several projects). For the 'platform' category, we find a steady growth in the number and especially length of cable projects (in average 10% of the total number of cables and 24% of the total length from 2019-2028).

In 2025 alone, platform corporations are involved in a total of 8 cable projects that together will cover 106.892 kilometers (13.361,5 km per cable in average), spanning more than half the length of all the cables with an RFS date in 2025 (60% of the total 174.823 km of cable). In comparison, the telcos are involved in 21 cable projects spanning shorter lengths (90,717 km in total; 4,775 per cable in average). Add to this that the group of platform corporations comprises a total of just three different market actors in 2025 (Meta, Google, and Amazon), while the telcos make up a group of 34 unique companies. A closer look at who the 34 are shows a dominance of the three incumbent Chinese telecommunications operators (China Telecom, China Mobile, and China Unicom) as well as Middle Eastern telcos (e.g., Omantel, Telecom Egypt, and Etisalat UAE).

As such, the Chinese telcos have managed to sustain and extend their presence in the submarine cable data industry, with none of the Chinese platform actors appearing in our dataset. A straightforward explanation for this is regulation: whereas the US telecommunications companies have long been banned from supplying services (Kushida, 2015), the large service providers have moved into the network layer without regulatory constraints. In China, the situation is the reverse: here, service providers are not allowed to invest in network infrastructure. This example clearly shows how political forces play a

crucial role in the evolution of the submarine data cable industry (as well as the rest of the digital market).

Despite the Chinese exceptions, we find that the rise of platform corporations in the submarine data cable industry reflects a broader reconfiguration of power across the digital market: Whereas the incumbent telcos had clear economic and technological advantages in the early phases of cable laying, the new digital market leaders now hold superior capital power and technological expertise. With the internet altering the fundamental conditions for service provision, the traditional revenue streams of legacy telcos (e.g., telephony and bundled TV packages) dry out, while those of platform corporations (e.g., data collection and targeted advertising) grow exponentially in mass and velocity.

As such, the asymmetry in investment power is only widening, with the platform corporations possessing almost inexorable investment capacities compared to those of national and regional actors. This allows them to move fast and build extensive, and often single-owned, cable projects while other actors depend on raising the necessary funds and collaborations. Importantly, several of Google's single-owned cables are also non-common carrier, meaning that they 'only' transport the company's own traffic, including that of their third-party collaborators (Google, 2018). As described by Winseck (2019), this is not a new strategy since the platforms have a history of establishing "parallel private internets [...] to serve the needs of the internet giants and voracious appetites of those they serve" (116).

In the past, this privatization was realized through contracting wholesalers such as Level 3, XO, and Cogent or content delivery network (CDN) suppliers such as Akamai and China Cache. Yet, the recent rise of private data cables indicates the emergence of an even more radical strategy of centralization and control. Officially, the private connections are promoted as a way of relieving common-carrier cables from the massive data loads supporting the platform corporations' fundamental business models and planned services (Google, 2018). However, it also contributes to creating walled-off gardens, where access to superior infrastructure follows the use of specific services, which further fuels the economic power of the platforms and drives off competitors.

Discussions & conclusions

The analysis above has traced a period marked by accelerating growth in global internet traffic, numerous groundbreaking digital innovations, and recurrent market disruptions. Corresponding with these broader changes, our analysis documents at least four important developments in the submarine data cable industry to discuss and examine more carefully:

first, we find a general proliferation of cables over time – even if some retire, many more enter, suggesting an increasing commercial and technological impact of this part of the internet infrastructure; second, we find a gradual decline in large telecommunications consortia in favor of more concentrated ownership around a few powerful platform corporations, indicating a shift in the underlying business models and funding strategies; third, we find an influx of companies from sectors outside of telecommunications reflecting this infrastructure’s increasing criticality and economic value; and finally, we find the rise in private cables, accompanying existing common-carrier cables, to be a central arena for future infrastructural power accumulation inside walled-off ecosystems.

In assessing and explaining these historical changes, we cannot look at submarine data cables as an isolated industry. The growth in cable systems and the commercial interests surrounding them, above all, speaks to the fact that the internet over the 40-year period went from being a supplementary communication technology to constituting a critical infrastructure. In this process, the supply of digital infrastructures evolved from being either a potentially profitable add-on to existing business models or a high-risk/high-gain investment opportunity to being one of the largest and most influential industries in the world, dominated by a few market leaders. These actors, in turn, possess the power to reshape the ‘rules of the game’ in ways that align with their own interests.

In the early days of the public internet, telecommunications corporations bore the economic risks in establishing an infrastructural foundation for others to build upon, while simultaneously placing themselves as key gatekeepers in the emerging digital economy. Alongside the growth of the internet and the success of the services running on top, new actors saw the commercial potential of the technology, leading to what can best be described as a ‘gold rush’ across internet layers in the 2000s. In the last phase, the material conditions for communicating are irrevocably transformed, leading to a reshuffling of institutional power and new forms of dependencies where ‘old’ actors increasingly rely on the ‘new’, rather than the other way around.

The developments described through the empirical example of submarine data cables, in other words, illustrate the secession of a historical type of incumbent and the potential emergence of a new one. Global platform corporations such as Google and Meta have gone from relying on external network operators transporting their ever-growing flows of data to becoming important backbone suppliers. On the one hand, they were born out of a period where the supply of communication services had been detached from the underlying networks, with services being offered on top of the infrastructure and at the edges of the

network. On the other hand, the same corporations can now be seen as leading a *reintegration* of the service and network layers, where the supply of superior services (e.g., AI models, cloud) is closely linked to having control of and access to the underlying infrastructure. Removing the intermediary, the platforms gain a cross-value chain control that allow them to supply connectivity that other actors depend on, either through the common carrier model or through the launch of private connections reserved for their own services and customers. The latter strategy shows the contours of an emergent, parallel infrastructure that can only be accessed through the usage of specific platforms, thereby contrasting fundamental principles that have been incremental for the development of the global internet.

The complex governance processes and business arrangements that have shaped these broad structural transformations are important topics for future research. Further enquiring into the commercial and geopolitical interests and negotiations surrounding contemporary and future submarine cable projects will enhance our understandings of how power is exerted through the ownership and control of this resource. Since our dataset is based solely on publicly available information, it has several blind spots relating to network capacities, monetary investments, and shares in fiber pairs that call for further enrichment of our analysis. Extending our variables and measures would allow for closer studies of the competition between different cable systems, provide insights into the actual costs of cable laying, and enable more precise economic calculations of the position of different market actors. Yet, hidden behind paywalls and proprietary data infrastructures funded by the very same stakeholders that we aim to study, such analyses come with a price attached and several economic, practical, ethical, and epistemic questions to consider for researchers and regulators alike.

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